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- The title and author(s) details should be on the first page. This should include telephone numbers and e-mail contacts.
- Author's name should be written in the following order: first name, other name and surname.
- The body of text should be in Times New Roman, properly justified in 12 pt. with 1.5line spacing.
- Referencing style is APA, 7th edition. All references should be listed in alphabetical order at the end of the article.
- The format for the body of article is: Introduction, Literature Review, Methodology, Results and Discussion, Conclusion and References. Also, authors should know that they are responsible for ensuring that:
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Russian- Ukraine Conflict and the Roles of United Nations

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Abstract

The hybrid conflict between Russia and Ukraine since 2013 have developed into dangerous global politics. Therefore, the objective of this study is to examine the politics of Russia towards Ukraine since independence in 1991; and Ukraine's desire to participate in European Union and NATO organizations. To Russians, Ukraine is a geopolitical misunderstanding, which openly violates concept of "Russkiy Mir" (Russian community). Russia aimed at maintaining its sphere of influence in terms of economy, politics and control over military potentials in the region. A real breakthrough was maiden annexation of Crimea, which resulted in the hybrid war in Ukraine. The research employed qualitative contents analysis method of secondary data using force theory as its framework. The study noted that historical grievances (displacement and exile) were the immediate and remote causes of Russian-Ukrainian Conflict. The findings shows that Russians were fighting a just course. The Conflict was traceable to the Cold War Era, and role politics played for Ukrainian government to participate in NATO, and EU. The New wars, called third wave is dominated by psychological and information-propaganda aspects, as well as guerrilla forces. The study recommends to UN that US should vacate its buffer Zone out of Ukraine, and to caution US about her activities and relations with Ukraine and Russian to avoid total holocaust.

Keywords: Conflict, Annexation, Geopolitical territory, International Organization, Cold War.

Introduction

Unpredictability and surprise constitute elementary conditions for the security of every country in the modern international relations. These features result from the dynamics of liability of the interstate situation over the centuries. An immeasurable metamorphosis of contemporary world order was the dissolution of the Soviet Union in December, 1991. The Union of Socialist Soviet Republic (USSR) as a subject of international law, a geopolitical power ceased to exist and a conglomerate consisting of 15 independent nations was formed. The interests, power and levels of political and economic development of these newly created countries varied from state to state. The Soviet Union, a country that extended across 22 million square kilometres and was inhabited by approximately 293 million people, 15 autonomous soviets with distinct culture, politics and economy emerged in 1991 as independent states (Aja, 1999). One of these countries was Ukraine. Others are; Armenia; Azerbaijan; Byelorussia; Estonia; Georgia; Kazakhstan; Kirghizia; Latvia; Lithuania; Moldavia; Russia Federation; Tajikistan; Turkmen; Uzbekistan (Kolkin, 2002).

The genesis of downturn in Soviet Union began in the middle 1980s when Mikhail Gorbachev on assumption as leader of USSR dramatically initiated reform programmes known as perestroika and glasnost in the economy and party leadership after decades of government censorship. These

reforms facilitated major arms control agreement in 1987 between President Ronald Regan and Mikhail Gorbachev on Intermediate Range Nuclear Force (INF). The INF resulted to reduction in number of nuclear weapons. Aja (1999 *ibid*: 217) stated that in 1988 Soviet Union withdrew their forces in Afghanistan and refused military support to most of its Communist satellite state in Eastern Europe resulting to overthrow of communist regimes in these countries. The eventual collapse of USSR began in 1989 when Gorbachev surprised the whole world by its decision to give up control over Eastern Europe, and the tearing down of Berlin Walls which led to East Germans unification with West Germany (Aja, 1999 *ibid*: 221). Chukwu, (2020: 139 – 141) identified the events that led to the disintegration of the former Soviet Union thus:

1. Bureaucratic and authoritarian system characterized by lack of democracy, freedom of speech and one party system – Communist Party, unaccountable to the people.
2. Dominance of Russian Republic in the Union, and neglect of the interests of other Autonomous Republics.
3. High expenditure on defence, low on infrastructure and technology among others.
4. Crisis in the Socialist Bloc, especially people from many East European countries. They protested against their own governments and USSR at the time of Soviet Union turmoil, the communist governments in those countries collapsed one after another.
5. The Fall of Berlin Wall was another catalyst to disintegration of USSR, because after the World War II, Germany was divided between the Socialist USSR and the Capitalist Western States led by United States of America. Thereafter USSR erected the Berlin wall to demarcate the boundaries of the two Germans.
6. Economic and Political reforms in USSR embarked by Gorbachev, which he identified as problems of USSR with the intention to revive the economy. This was a deviation from the communist policies, and his new approach was more closely associated with market driven economy. Many communist hard liners in USSR opposed Gorbachev reforms; they encouraged coup against Gorbachev in 1991.
7. Opposition against the coup by Boris Yeltsin who won popular election in Russian Republic. Yeltsin protested against the coup and the central control of USSR – freedom for republics became the slogan. Yeltsin alongside with pluralist movement advocated for democratization and rapid economic reforms, while the hard line Communist elite wanted to thwart Gorbachev's reform agenda.
8. Power shift from Soviet center to republics, especially republics like Russia, Ukraine and Belarus emerged powerful. These republics declared that the Soviet Union was disbanded. The decision to split USSR into independent republics was not a joint decision because Central Asian countries wanted to remain inside USSR. But decision was taken against their choice.

Indeed, Mikhail Gorbachev was relatively young and inexperienced unlike the Soviet Union hard liners like Brezhnev, Yuri Andropov and Konstantin Cherenkov; and of which President Vladimir Putin was one strong believer in Russian communist centralization policy. On June 1990, Boris Yeltsin was elected chairman of Congress of Peoples' Deputies. He declared Russian Federation a sovereign territory and proceeded to pass laws that superseded some of the USSR laws (Ellison, 2006). The situation resulted to political turmoil as Soviet Union and Russian Federation leadership

wrestled for control, culminating to 1991 putsch where the hardliners attempted to overthrow Gorbachev in order to reverse his reforms and reassert the central government control over the republics (Ellison, 2006 *ibid*)

Obviously, the Russian conflict with Ukraine is a political strategy of Vladimir Putin to navigate his ambition in order to unify its former allies into one umbrella (Chukwu, 2020 *ibid*: 142). Putin took over power from Boris Yeltsin in 2000, and have ruled Russia for more than two decades. On the other hands, Ukraine relationship with North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) began when Ukraine joined North Atlantic Cooperation Council in 1994 Partnership for Peace programme (Snyder, 2018). But, Ukraine aspiration for NATO membership dates back to 2008 Bucharest Summit, where NATO leaders agreed that Ukraine would become a member in 2023. This led to NATO – Ukraine Council to further integrate Ukraine into the alliance. Vladimir Putin know fully well that 2023 Ukraine membership to NATO was fast approaching annexed Crimea in March 2014 as first and litmus test phase to bring back its allies (DeBenedictis, 2022).

In February, 2022, the conflict escalated into full scale second phase invasion. In this phase, Russia rolled its tanks into Ukraine making it one of the deadliest wars in Eastern Europe after World War II. The Kremlin's method of the war is hybrid. It is based on psychological and information propaganda kinds of politics towards Ukraine since 1991. The dissolution of the USSR, and Ukraine intense aspiration to join NATO and its European partners has been a bone to Russian contention for a new integration agreement, consociating the majority of states in the former Soviet Union as a political jurisdiction.

Statement of the Problem

The conflict between the West-East blocs had been an eternal problem to the world peace and development in international relations. The West championed by the US while the East was championed by the defunct USSR. As the rivalry continue after the second World War, little wonder with the collapse-of the former USSR in 1991, the rivalry still persist into the 21st century a new development in form of new Russian-Ukrainian war owing to the fact that US have offered to make Ukrainian one of its buffer zone. Despite numerous peace efforts over the past several decades aimed at resolving the Russian-Ukrainian rivalry through negotiations and other means of conflict resolution, the conflict persists with no end in sight. Many factors have hindered previous peace efforts, including potential venue for sustainable peace between the two states. A lot has been done by world bodies like the United Nations to achieve long lasting peace in this region but that has yielded no positive result. The research is interested to examine the inability of UN as a global peace organization to resolve the conflict of annexation Ukraine by Russia in line with Article 1(1) as she did in Iraq and some other parts of the world. Therefore, the UN inaction to act against a multipolar state has posed a dangerous precedence in the international community.

Objectives of the Study

This study will unravel the factors driving the emergence of this new war between the two sovereign states. However, the following under – listed are the specific objectives of the study:

1. To examine the history and politics of the Russia-Ukraine Conflict.
2. To examine the reason and desire by Ukraine to participate in some International Organization.

3. To examine the United Nations roles in the Russian – Ukraine Conflict

Literature Review

Conceptual Clarification

War

War can be physical or ideological antagonism, a fight, or disagreement between two countries; it can involve the use of weapons and other instruments of war. War is often regarded as a behaviour of nations in the international system (Morgan, 1984: 255). Akinboye & Ottob, (2005: 143 - 144) war can be caused through regime type; interactive behaviour which often times generates spiral hostility; lateral pressure usually through trade, investment, and conquest of colonies; arms race; deterrence and other forms of threat. Clausewitz (1832), “War is the continuation of policy with other means”. Every era has its wars, which is why war over the last decades has gradually and intangibly changed its character. Alvin & Heidi (1980: 32), wrote about the dimension of a modern war. This couple examine the aspects of modern war. The main thesis of their publication “War and anti-war” is that there are three civilisation waves, which relate directly to all three waves of war. The first one mentioned by the authors is the agrarian wave, the second is called industrial and the third – modern (post-industrial). The symbols of each are respectively: a hoe, an assembly belt and a computer, which represent those waves of wars. The wars of the so-called third wave are characterised by the constant formation of a post-Cold War international order through the application and use of force. In other words, therefore, Force becomes inevitable when other means of conflict resolution have failed to achieve the desired goals.

Characteristics of the Third Wave of War

- The parties to conflict are usually public actors, paramilitary groups, mercenaries controlled by powers (privatisation of war);
- Dissymmetry, which means that parties to the conflict are not equal;
- It is hard to define the opponent, the aims of the war and determine the beginning and the end of the conflict;
- There are very often cultural, ethnic, and religious roots of the conflict;
- Strategic places and institutions for the state are to be destroyed, since they are a target.
- The next aim may be the malfunction of an economic situation (short-term) in a particular country, in relation to the above-mentioned actions (e.g. a drop in the values of shares of the listed companies);
- Civilians are the main victims;
- Unfavourable media propaganda, which is to worsening the image of a certain country on the international level;
- Illegal and harmful activity in cyberspace;
- They are often wars of internal characters, which become international with time.
- The parties to the conflict are financed through organised crime, selling natural resources, and other illegal sources (Alvin & Heidi, 1980: *ibid* 33)

Conflict

Conflicts refer to a struggle or clash between opposing forces. Obizulike – Osuofia (2013: 17 - 19), conflict is not to be avoided, but to be managed. It is a struggle and a clash of interests, opinions, or even principles. Conflict will always be found in society, because the basis of conflict may vary from personal to racial, class, caste, political and international. Therefore, the political imbroglio in Ukraine can easily be classified as a conflict even though it is gradually degenerating into war, which has been the *raison de eta* of this study. It is a social phenomenon arising from disagreement in policies, ideologies and actions of one group or nation against another. However, a military conflict, apart from war, encompasses armed intervention, armed incident, military coup, military blockage, and perhaps demonstration of power, among other things. Aja, (2007: 15) defined conflict as an attitude, a behaviour or an action or a process that introduces strains and stresses in a relationship between two or more parties on attainment of set interests or goals. Akinboye & Ottoh, (2005 *ibid*: 139 - 140) enumerated causes of conflicts as - national prestige, bridge of expectations, acquisition, imperialism, ideological extremisms, mutual distrust, and human aggressive behaviour. Some of these causes are factors in Russia-Ukraine conflict.

Theoretical Framework

Force Theory

In international relations, force is the use of coercion, threat or violence to influence the behaviour of other states or actors (Clausewitz 1832). This was manifested by Russia against Ukraine on annexation of Crimea and four regions of Ukraine in order to protect their interest. Force can be applied through the use of military maneuvering, economic and political sanctions, blockade or both. Acquisition of power in international relations influences behaviours of state to use force to obtain its goals. Force theory are drawn from various discipline. Some key factors that ginger states to resort to force are - territorial disputes, security and ideological differences. Russia under Vladimir Putin have demonstrated aggressive behaviour for the past years in office. He is mindful to protect, defend the territory perimeter and the ideology of communist manifestos. Dinstein's (2017) theory of force illuminated a comprehensive analysis of *jus contra bellum* of war, aggression and self-defence. To him, there are laws in international relations that regulate states from using force against each other, for example, Article 2(4) of the UN Charter prohibits the threat or use of force against an independent state. The UN could not exploit this provision against Russia; rather, the Kremlin exploited Article 51 on self-defence against an envisaged threat, because Ukraine's interest in joining NATO is perceived as undermining Russian security. Therefore, Russia, to safeguard its interests and the Empire, applied force theory in line with Clausewitz's theory of force, which simply stated that "War is the continuation of policy with other means".

Methodology

The research design for this study is descriptive, utilising qualitative content analysis to examine the roles of the UN in the Ukraine–Russia conflict (2022-2025). The study examined the politics between Russia and Ukraine, the root cause of the war, and Ukraine's relations with

its international partners. The data for this research were collected through a systematic literature review (SLR) of secondary data obtained from textbooks, international journals and magazines, as well as online media, regarding the UN's roles in the Russia-Ukraine conflict. The data was analysed thematically in line with stated objectives.

Results

Politics of Russian Federation toward Ukraine

Russian Federation is viewed as a world power within the circles of international relations with 17 million square kilometres is one of the largest country in the world by surface area, extending across 2 continents –Europe and Asia (Kolkin, 2022 *ibid*). It is also one of the most populous countries with about 143.5 million people and a vast potential of energy resources among the former USSR states. Russia is one of the world's leading producers of natural gas and oil. It is in third place, after Saudi Arabia and the USA, in the production of oil, and second to USA when it comes to the extraction of gas. Possession of natural resources and the possibility of its extraction and processing puts Russia on a pedestal in the global political arena. Oil, as well as gas and nuclear energy are key instruments in international politics (Kolkin, 2022: *ibid*).

On the other hand, Ukraine is the second largest country (after Russia) in Eastern Europe, since it has an area of 603,500 square kilometers, and its population is around 45 million. Ukraine is not very rich in natural resources. The Ukrainian economy is mostly based on agriculture, thanks to its fertile soils. The most significant natural resources of Ukraine are iron ore, black coal, manganese, and, in minor quantities, gas, and oil (Rasler, etal 2000). After the dissolution of the Soviet Union, the politics of the Russian Federation was aimed at stopping Ukraine acquiring a western legacy, a norm and values created by West as Atlanticism and Neo-Eurasians (Potocki, . etal 2014). The task of Russia is to become a world power, and to regain and maintain its influence in the post-Soviet zones. Aleksandr, (1997) was a leading Russian neo – Eurasian theorist. He singles out two opposite civilizations, which compete with one another in a natural way, aiming at confrontation; these are the Eastern and Western civilizations. His vision concerning the place of Russia in the contemporary world is inspired by these words: “Whoever rules East Europe commands the Heartland; whoever rules the Heartland commands the World Island; whoever rules the World Island commands the World”. Based on this, the Russian foreign policies were directed in objecting increasing domination of USA in post-Soviet states. Aleksandr, (1997: *ibid*) also made the following comment concerning Ukraine: “The sovereignty of Ukraine is a negative phenomenon for the geopolitics of Russia and may cause a military conflict. Ukraine, as a sovereign country, with its territorial ambitions, may pose a threat to the whole of Eurasia. Strategically, Ukraine should be a projection of Russia in the South and in the West”. He recommended the concept of pragmatic consensus and multipolar world order. The notion of pragmatic consensus was officially presented in UN, by Yevgeny Primakov (former Prime Minister of the Russia Federation) was at the 51st session of the UN General Assembly. He believed that the world should be multipolar and that Russia should play a key role in it. The idea of pragmatic consensus presupposes the achievement of the following five main aims.

- a. It would be the renewal of the position of Russia as a main player on the territory of the former Soviet Union. In the future, it also assumes the transformation of the Commonwealth of Independent States in an integrated region of the world, capable of development and maintenance of stability.
- b. It establishes the usage of the resources attained in the era of the USSR.
- c. Thirdly, it will be for the diversification of contacts with the West.
- d. Fourthly, it will aim at increasing cooperation with Asia, mainly China and India.
- e. Fifthly, it will use Russia as the country relating Europe with Asia (Aleksandr, 1997: *ibid*)

In foreign politics of Russia, Vladimir Putin, has never treated the countries of the former USSR as fully independent states. Russia's strategic assumptions have been that these states occupy a certain territory, have a Russian identity, belong to and remain within its sphere of influence.

Reasons for the Conflict in Ukraine

There are numerous causes for the outbreak of conflict in Ukraine. However, the main reason is connected with Ukraine's active interest in participation in Western association structures, such as the European Union and NATO. Ukraine's relations with the European Union started in 1994, when the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement was signed. During the following years, they achieved this within the framework of the European Neighbourhood Policy and Eastern Partnership, which was expected to be established in Ukraine. In 2009, Ukraine was invited to join the Eastern Partnership Project, established within the framework of the European Neighbourhood Policy. Poland was also involved in signing the Association Agreement between Ukraine and the European Union in 2012. In June 2012, the European Parliament decided to send a mission to Ukraine. The delegation consisted of Pat Cox (Ireland) and Aleksander Kwaśniewski (Poland). Despite various objections, the EU maintained a positive approach towards Ukraine.

Aleksandr Kwasniewski, the head of the EU Parliament monitoring delegation, noted thus: "Europe needs Ukraine, considering its demographic potential, its market, millions of Ukrainians employed in EU countries, as well as in Poland. Ukraine is ready to accept our standards, as opposed to Belarus or Russia". Contrary to the dreams and full involvement of Ukrainians, on 21st November 2013, a week before the summit of the East Partnership, the contemporary government of Ukraine (under the influence of Moscow) suspended the preparations for signing the Ukraine-European Union Association Agreement. Prime Minister Mykola Azarov, on approval of President Viktor Yanukovich gave his opinion, announced that Ukraine, in the interest of national security, would not sign this document. Next day in Maiden - Kiev main square, where Orange Revolution took place in 2004, more than 2000 people gathered to protest. It began a bloody strike against taking away the dreams of a better future from the citizens of Ukraine. It was the birth of the so called Euro-maiden (Gil, 2014). The hot spot at Maiden encompassed non-governmental organizations, academia and pressure group oriented intellectuals gathered in hundreds. This was why Euro-maiden is called the Revolution of Dignity. There was a tense situation in the Western part of Ukraine on the 21st and 22nd of February 2014, the Eastern Ukrainian Russian-speaking community began to notice the need for sovereignty. After the events at the Maiden, Eastern Ukraine began to manifest its distinction and independence. The same feelings also occurred with Crimea (Gil, 2014). Ukraine, as a country, is divided into 4 main zones: Western, Central, Eastern

and Southern. From the very beginning of Ukraine's independence, its national identity was built on diverse social attitudes. The sense of belonging to Ukraine was felt mainly by the inhabitants of the Western and Central regions. The inhabitants of Eastern and Southern Ukraine differ because people living there were mostly Russian-speaking. The distinctive feature of the East and Southern regions is relatively limited knowledge of economic liberalism and liberal democracy. The two regions have been longing for the days of non-liberal democracy of the Soviet-type and the economic politics of real socialism (Gil, 2014 *ibid*).

United Nations and International Partners' Responses to Russia – Ukraine Conflict

The United Nations has taken some initiatives and responses towards halting the crisis in the Ukraine territory notably according to Daniel (2025).

- In 2022, the General Assembly adopted a resolution condemning Russia's attempted annexation of four Ukrainian cities – Donetsk, Kherson, Luhansk and Zaporizhzhia. The resolution was supported by 143 votes, 5 against and 35 absented.
- The UN has set up high level human rights monitoring group to collate evidences of human rights violations and abuses in Ukraine for accountability, and
- The General Assembly of UN had approved Commission to investigate war crime in Ukraine backed by documented evidences of Russian war crimes, torture, rape and deportation of children to Russia.

Indeed, the UN responses to investigate Russian action and to take decisive action is limited by the veto power in permanent Security Council members including Russia. Daniel (2025: *ibid*) Wall Street Journal in response to Russia invasion, stated that NATO troops carried out drills in February 2025 a mile from Ukraine border to test a quick reaction force over increasing dimensions of Russian attacks. The NATO's military muscle was unusual because European nations carried out the exercise without United States of America. The European Union had made strong proposals of military stacks against Russian without US support according to the WSJ reporter. But US President Donald Trump said a lot of work had to be done ahead of his planned talk with the Russian leader in terms of ending the conflict in Ukraine.

Discussion

Economic and Humanitarian Impact

The conflict has decimated the Ukrainian environment, causing great floods, wildfires and pollution, resulting in several soot and other ecological damages. Drone footage shows evidence of a war crime against Russia. The New York Times Magazine, 4th April 2025, reported the execution of prisoners of war near Novoivanovka in the Kursk region of Russia. Again, the New York Times also reported on 5th April 2025, that Zelenskyy's home, Kryvyi Rih, was attacked, 16 people were killed by Russian drones, while cease-fire talks with the American envoy were ongoing. The Magazine noted that the attack targeted Western military instructors in Ukraine. On 7th April 2025, in central Kyiv, Sumy, northeastern Ukraine, thirty-two people were killed (New York Times Magazine of 13th April 2025).

Diplomatic Effort

Georgi & Lytvynenko (2025). WSJ reporters said US President Donald Trump had expressed his intention to stop the conflict in Ukraine, but Russian Foreign Minister Sergei Lavrov demanded international recognition of Russian control over Crimea and four other Ukrainian regions. The Russian president, Vladimir Putin, had in 2024 rejected an immediate ceasefire with Ukraine, accusing the United States of America of acting in the interest of Ukraine. The New York Times, 30th March, 2025, noted untold stories of America's hidden roles in Ukraine against the Russian invading armies. The Magazine noted that the secret partnership was based out of U.S military garrison command in Wiesbaden, Germany. The report noted that the command is guiding big picture battle strategy and precision targeting information down to soldiers in the field.

On April 11, 2025, a senior U.S. diplomat, Steve Witkoff, was in Moscow to reignite talks over the conflict in Ukraine that had stalled (New York Times, April 30, 2025). The Ukrainian president, Volodymyr Zelenskyy, expressed little faith in the latest effort to halt fighting with Russia, as Vladimir Putin has used past pauses in fighting to gain more ground. Zelenskyy said: "As soon as they announced a ceasefire, the one who observes it is the one who loses" (WSJ Magazine, 13th March, 2025). Oksana & Warson (2025) WSJ, for example, reported that when Artem Kravchenko and hundreds of Ukrainian soldiers at Ilovaisk in 2024, put their trust in the Russian promise and retreated, the Russian army came forcefully against the Ukrainian army. The inability of President Trump to secure a peaceful deal in Ukraine has left him frustrated. Trump wants Moscow to get a concession deal in order to stop the conflict. However, President Putin is also mindful of the stick-and-carrot approach employed by Donald Trump during the Ukraine crisis (Oksana & Warson, 2025). For instance, the New York Times Magazine of 30th March, 2025, disclosed that President Trump had threatened to impose secondary tariffs on Russia's oil if Putin thwarted negotiations on a cease-fire deal with Ukraine again.

Prospects and Challenges

At 2024 Washington summit, NATO pledged long time bilateral security assistance to Ukraine including training, capacity building and supply of equipment (Shuster, 2024). According to Shuster, NATO in addition alongside with the European Union has also imposed severe sanctions on Russia for its aggression against Ukraine. In another summit of NATO in London, the cease -fire agreement with American Secretary of State Marco Rubio suffered a setback when the Secretary of State pulled out of the meeting. Kirchick, (2025) quoted the European Union members at the meeting thus: "If America walked away, European Union sees Ukraine security as vital to European security, and so we are much prepared to keep supporting Ukraine" Kirchick also noted that the White House proposals to end the conflict was not acceptable to President Zelenskyyr who also drew his own counteroffer which contradicts Trump demands from Kremlin. Perhaps, the Secretary of States pulling out from NATO meeting would not have been unconnected to America legalizing annexation of some Ukraine territories.

Conclusion

The conflict in Ukraine is setting a dangerous precedent in international relations. The fact that Russia is a member of the UN Security Council is undermining the efforts of the United Nations sanctions against Russia as a belligerent state. Again, the inability of the Trump administration to halt the conflict on a peace deal has left him increasingly frustrated, tearing NATO configurations apart. The European states are acting helplessly. The key player is Vladimir Putin. He views the European Union and NATO as threats to the Russian Federation's survival. (Oksana & Warson 2025: *ibid*)

Recommendations

1. There is a need for the United Nations to ask the United States of America to pull out its buffer zone in Ukraine and other military garrison commands in Western and Eastern Europe to guarantee Russian trust in the region.
2. As a global peace organisation, the UN should request Ukraine to conduct a referendum for the Russian-speaking territories of East and Southern Ukraine, hence only the West and Central parts of Ukraine are in alignment with the Ukrainian government.
3. There should be more diplomatic negotiation on the platform of the United Nations General Assembly rather than negotiating only with the United States of America and its European allies.
4. Ukraine should recognise that its ambition to join NATO and the European Union is a threat to the survival of the Russian Federation. The consequences are catastrophic; no nation would like to lose sight of the enemy's timetable.

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